

A BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION STRATEGY FOR THE VHEMBE BIOSPHERE RESERVE BASED ON A REVISION OF ZONATION

Compiled by the Conservation Task Team of the VBR

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1. BACKGROUND

1.1 Status quo

Fig. 1 shows the existing configuration of core (dark green), buffer (light green) and transitional (grey) zones. Legislated Provincial Nature Reserves and National Parks make up the core areas and relatively pristine areas surrounding them have been designated as buffer zones although no public participation with landowners took place. No conservation targets were set and no attempt was made to ensure that biodiversity is adequately conserved.

Figure1. Existing core (dark green), buffer (light green) and transition (grey) zones of the VBR

In 2015 Ledet appointed the company Strategic Environmental Focus (Pty) Ltd to compile a Strategic Environmental Management Plan (SEMP) for the VBR. A status quo report was presented in February 2016. After this some issues arose around the funding of the project and in September 2016 the company submitted a final report with the heading “Desired State of the Environment Report with Environmental Management Guidelines”. This report, now referred to as the SEM, was approved as a guideline for the rezoning of the VBR at a Board Meeting held on 1 June 2018. The Board also requested the Conservation Task Team to compile a biodiversity conservation strategy based on the SEM guidelines.

1.2 Proposals in the Environmental Management Guidelines of the SEMP

The SEMP bases its division of the VBR into core, buffer and transitional zones mainly on key environmental and biophysical landscape features as well as species data.

Based on this, the SEMP proposes that the VBR be zoned as shown in Fig 2. It must be noted that most of the smaller dark green patches represent private nature reserves legislated under the previous Transvaal Provincial Administration. Many of the owners of these properties are not aware that their properties are nature reserves and they are generally not managed as such any more. However, they are important because they represent legal conservation areas.

Figure 2. Proposed zonation in the SEMP (core in dark green, buffer in light green and transition in orange)

Fig. 3 shows that the core areas proposed in the SEMP are very similar to the CBA1 areas in the Ledet C-plan and the buffer zones are basically identical to CBA2 areas. As far as we could determine Ledet has not yet published a protection expansion strategy. Fig.3 shows that the western Soutpansberg, Blouberg, an area below Musina and an area below Louis Trichardt are identified as priority areas for conservation expansion in the NPAES. Inclusion of a core and buffer zone south of Louis Trichardt in the SEMP is in line with the NPAES.

Figure 3. Critical Biodiversity Areas 1 (dark green) and 2 (light green) in the Ledet C-plan and areas of the VBR identified as priority areas for conservation expansion in the National Protected Areas Expansion Strategy (shown in light brown)

The SEMP does not refer to targets or include any information on vegetation types, drivers of ecosystems or rare species conservation.

2. A BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION PLAN FOR THE VBR BASED ON REZONING OF THE CORE, BUFFER AND TRANSITIONAL ZONES.

2.1 Introduction

This report will be discussed at a workshop of Task Team members and other interested stakeholders before it is finalized.

The objective of this exercise was to propose a reconfiguration of the core buffer and transitional zones in such a way that the biodiversity conservation function of the VBR can be effectively implemented. Although this exercise was only aimed at biodiversity conservation the Task Team realized that the ultimate aim should be to support, promote and achieve, within the VBR, a balanced and sustainable relationship between socio-economic development, the conservation of biodiversity and the sustainable use of natural resources on which people's livelihoods depend (The South African Strategy for the Biosphere Reserve Programme (2016-2020)- Department of Environmental Affairs).

We propose three targets in our conservation plan namely vegetation types, the drivers of vegetation types and species.

We used the published SANBI conservation targets for vegetation types as our goal. The conservation targets for vegetation types that occur in the VBR varies from 19 to 100%, the assumption being that 75% of species will be included if the target is reached. For example, the assumption is that the Limpopo Sweet

Bushveld, with a conservation target of 19%, if achieved, should conserve 75% of species that occur in this vegetation type.

Drivers of vegetation types are complex and poorly understood and can be very difficult to manage. However, local impacts by factors such as fire, runoff and the impacts of animals can be managed to a certain extent and we can also plan for anticipated global climate change. This aspect will receive attention when management plans are compiled and will not be discussed in this report.

The target for species is to include all red data species within core conservation areas Obviously we could only work with those taxa of which red data lists are available.

Species that occur in meta-populations such as leopard, lion, elephant, cheetah and wild dog should also receive individual attention if we are serious about their long-term conservation.

2.2 Vegetation types and their conservation

Unfortunately the SANBI vegetation maps are not accurate but we obviously did not have time to re-map them and just had to work with the available information hoping that it will not impact significantly on the outcome.

Each of the 25 terrestrial vegetation types that occur in the VBR are described individually.

Subtropical Alluvial vegetation

Occurs along the Limpopo and Shingwedzi Rivers. The conservation target is 31 % and it is considered to be well conserved with 70% included in conservation areas nationally (SANBI). Approximately 40% of this vegetation type in the VBR is conserved in the Maspungubwe and Kruger National Parks and conservation expansion is therefor not required based on the SANBI target. However, this vegetation type is complex and poorly surveyed and we recommend that the remaining areas outside the parks also be conserved and that no further fragmentation be allowed. We propose that these areas be legislated as protected environments in terms of Section 28 of NEMPAA. They will have to be mapped for this purpose.

Lowveld Riverine Forest

The SANBI Vegetation Map shows Lowveld Riverine Forest only to occur in the Pafuri area and a small section upstream along the Limpopo River. This is probably not correct and this vegetation type needs to be properly defined and mapped in the VBR. In the meantime we have to rely on the National Forest Act (84 of 1998) to provide protection. The conservation target is 100% and all forests are protected under this act. The minister can also declare certain forests as Forest Nature Reserves.

Subtropical Salt Pans

The SANBI Vegetation Map only identifies three Subtropical Salt Pans. All three are situated on commercial farms north of the Soutpansberg outside existing core

areas, two of which are privately owned and the third is partly privately and partly government owned. All three properties will be visited as part of the public participation process to determine whether the owners are willing to apply for private nature reserve status through the Stewardship Programme. If the owners are not willing to do this, an attempt will be made to get at least the areas surrounding the salt pans legislated in some way.

Vegetation types that occur totally inside the Kruger National Park within the VBR and require no conservation expansion (Fig. 4)

- **Nwambyia - Pumbe Sandy Bushveld**
- **Mopane Basalt Shrubland**
- **Cathedral Mopane Bushveld**
- **Sand Forest**
- **Northern Lebombo Bushveld**
- **Mopane Grubbo Shrubland**

Figure 4. Vegetation types that occur totally inside the Kruger National Park (Musina et al., 2005)

Limpopo Ridge Bushveld

The conservation target for Limpopo Ridge Bushveld is 19%. Roughly 20% is already included in legislated conservation areas so conservation expansion is not required (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 The occurrence of Limpopo Ridge Bushveld, Musina Mopani Bushveld, and Limpopo Sweet Bushveld in the VBR (Musina et al., 2005)

Musina Mopani Bushveld

This is the largest of the vegetation types that occur in the VBR (Fig. 5). The SANBI conservation target is 19%. Presently only 1.4 % is legally protected in existing core areas.

Limpopo Sweet Bushveld

Based on the SANBI vegetation map approximately 2.7% of this vegetation type is presently conserved in the Langjan NR (Fig. 6). Preliminary discussion with some landowners indicate that it should not be difficult to reach the target of 19% for this vegetation type through the Stewardship Programme. The true boundary of the vegetation type extends further north and east than shown in the SANBI map.

Figure 6. Occurrence of Limpopo Sweet Bushveld in the VBR based on Musina et al. (2005).

Roodeberg Bushveld

Approximately 11% of Roodeberg Bushveld in the VBR is conserved in the Blouberg and Maleboch Nature Reserves (Fig. 7). An attempt will be made to

extend its conservation through the Stewardsip Programme in the area north of the Blouberg Nature Reserve.

Figure 7. The occurrence of Roodeberg Bushveld in the VBR (Musina et al., 2005)

Makhado Sweet Bushveld

None of the 19% target is presently conserved in core conservation areas in the VBR. Public participation will therefore focus on expanding conservation through the Stewardship Programme, concentrating in the area south of Louis Trichardt (red) prioritized in the National Protection Areas Expansion Strategy (NPAES) (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. The occurrence of Makhado Sweet Bushveld in the VBR, based on Musina et al., 2005

Tzaneen Sour Bushveld

This vegetation type is listed as threatened. It is presently not conserved in core areas of the VBR (Fig. 9) and it is largely fragmented (fragmented areas in yellow). It may be possible to establish some private nature reserves on the western side of its range and around the Albasini Dam. Red shows the NPAES priority area.

Figure 9. The occurrence of Tzaneen Sour Bushveld in the VBR, based on Musina et al., 2005)

Granite Lowveld

Granite Lowveld, shown in pink in Fig. 10, with disturbed areas in yellow is also largely fragmented. There are no government or private nature reserves within this vegetation type in the VBR.

Figure 10. The occurrence of Granite Lowveld in the VBGR, based on Musina et al. 2005.

Tsende Mopaneveld

This vegetation type (yellow in Fig. 11) occurs in two areas, a narrow section on the western boundary of the KNP and a larger area in the catchment of the Shingwedzi River and extending into a communal area outside the park with marked transformation (shown in pink). No conservation extension is required because most of the vegetation type occurs in the KNP.

Figure 11. The occurrence of Tsende Mopaneveld in the VBR, based on Musina, et al., 2005.

Lowveld Rugged Mopaneveld

A small patch of this vegetation type protrudes into the southern part of the VBR along the Shingwedzi River. Thirty four percent of the total ecosystem is conserved in the KNP outside the VBR so no conservation extension is required in the VBR.

Makuleke Sandy Bushveld

Makuleke Sandy Bushveld (grey in Fig. 12) covers a large area in the northern part of the KNP and extends into the Venda area. A small patch also occurs on the Shingwedzi River. More than the target of 19% is included in the KNP so no conservation extension is required.

Figure 12. The occurrence of Makuleke Sandy Bushveld in the VBR, based on Musina et al., 2005.

Ironwood Dry Forest

In the SANBI Vegetation Map the Ironwood Dry Forest is plotted as isolated patches, all within the northern part of the KNP. However, it is well known that this vegetation type also occurs relatively widespread outside the KNP. Fortunately it occurs mostly in rocky habitats that are not suitable for cultivation so it should be relatively safe until its distribution and status can be assessed more

accurately. The conservation target is 100% so legislation will have to be applied to conserve it outside the KNP.

Vhavenda Miombo

Vhavenda Miombo is a small patch of vegetation (36ha) dominated by the tree species *Brachystegia speciformis* that occurs east of the Nwanedi Nature Reserve (Fig. 13). The conservation target of 100% is reached in the Brackenridgia Nature Reserve but the size of the reserve has to be increased for effective conservation.

Figure 13. The location of Vhavenda Miombo in the VBR, based on Musina, et al., 2005.

Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld

Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld (light purple in Fig. 14) covers a large area in Makgabeng, Blouberg and Soutpansberg. It is very complex with a variety of subtypes. The conservation target is 25% but only about 2% is presently conserved in core areas.

Figure 14. The occurrence of Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld (light purple) in the VBR according to Musina et al., 2005

Northern Mistbelt Forest

Northern Mistbelt Forest occurs as fragmented patches in the Blouberg and Soutpansberg. According to SANBI only 11% is conserved while the target is 30%. This figure is speculative because the forests have not been mapped in detail. This vegetation type is very important for biodiversity conservation and under a lot of stress and we recommend a target of 100%.

Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld

This vegetation type also occurs as fragmented patches in the upper reaches of the Soutpansberg and Blouberg with different subtypes. It is characterized by a high diversity of endemic plant and animal species. Although SANBI states that 17% is conserved the figure is probably much lower. The conservation target is 24%. We recommend a higher conservation target .

Northern Escarpment Afromontane Fynbos

This vegetation type is still unmapped and occurs in fragments on the summits of the Soutpansberg and Blouberg. The SANBI conservation target is 27% and they suggest that 56% is conserved. We do not agree with this figure and suggest a target of 100%.

2.3 A summary of the conservation status and targets of vegetation types

The following nine vegetation types are adequately conserved in existing conservation areas and conservation expansion is not required to reach the SANBI targets.

VEG. TYPE	% IN VBR IN SA +/-	% OF TOTAL CON-SERVED	CONS. TARGET %	% CONS. IN VBR	SURFACE AREA IN VBR HA	CONS. AREA TO BE ADDED IN VBR (HA)
Vhavenda Miombo	100	100	100	100	36	0
Limpopo Ridge Bushveld	100	20	19	20	264400	0
Cathedral Mopane Bushveld	100	95	19	100	28700	0
Mopane Basalt Shrubland	30	95	19	100	90100	0
Tsende Mopane Veld	30	61	19	90	143100	0
Makuleke Sandy Bushveld	100	30	19	30	206600	0
Nwambyia	100	92	19	100	15400	0

Pumbe Sandy Bushveld						
Northern Lebombo Bushveld	5	98	24	100	2300	0
Sand Forest	5	42	100	100	1600	0

The SANBI conservation targets for vegetation types are not reached in the following nine vegetation types. It will be difficult to reach the target for Roodeberg Bushveld, Lowveld Rugged Mopaneveld and Granite Lowveld Bushveld due to the nature of land tenure. It may be possible to extend conservation in Roodeberg Bushveld once we have a more accurate vegetation map. The target for Lowveld Rugged Mopaneveld is reached outside the VBR so we suggest that we stick with this. Seventeen % of Granite Lowveld Bushveld is also conserved outside the VBR so this should be acceptable. Sufficient areas of commercial farms exist in the Limpopo Sweet Bushveld, Makhado Sweet Bushveld, Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld, Musina Mopane Bushveld, Tzaneen Sour Bushveld and Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld to reach the targets through the Stewardship Programme.

VEG. TYPE	% IN VBR IN SA +/-	% OF TOTAL CON-SERVED	CONS. TARGET %	% CONS. IN VBR	SURFACE AREA IN VBR HA	CONS. AREA TO BE ADDED IN VBR (HA)
Roodeberg Bushveld	25	6	19	8	134500	14800
Limpopo Sweet Bushveld	30	1	19	2.7	191600	31230
Makhado Sweet Bushveld	25	1	19	0	400000	76760
Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld	100	2	25	2	447800	103000
Musina Mopane Bushveld	95	2	19	1.4	924300	162000
Lowveld Rugged Mopaneveld	5	32	19	0	11100	2100
Granite Lowveld Bushveld	60	17	19	0	165500	5206
Tzaneen Sour Bushveld	30	1	19	0	96500	18300
Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld	100	17	24	12	9400	1128

This leaves us with the following six vegetation types of which we do not have even fairly reliable distribution maps. Northern Escarpment Afromontane Fynbos and Northern Mistbelt Forest will be captured if we can conserve the upper reaches of the Blouberg and Soutpansberg. The conservation target for both should be 100% (all forests are supposed to be conserved in any case). In order to achieve the target for Ironwood Dry Forest, all the existing patches outside the KNP will have to be mapped accurately. Lowveld Riverine Forest, Subtropical Alluvial Vegetation and Subtropical pans also have to be mapped accurately. The conservation target should be 100% for all three.

VEG. TYPE	% IN VBR IN SA +/-	% OF TOTAL CON-SERVED	CONS. TARGET %	% CONS. IN VBR	SURFACE AREA IN VBR HA	CONS. AREA TO BE ADDED IN VBR (HA)
Northern Escarpment Afromontane Fynbos	?	56	27	?	?	?
Northern Mist-belt Forest	?	11	30	?	?	?
Ironwood Dry Forest	?	?	100	?	?	?
Lowveld Riverine Forest	?	?	100	?	?	?
Subtropical Alluvial Vegetation	?	?	31	?	?	?
Subtropical Salt Pans	?	20	24	0	?	?

2.4 Proposed conservation expansion to reach the targets for vegetation types.

Three methods are proposed to reach the targets namely:

- The Stewardship Programme in commercial farming areas
- Discussions with community leaders in communal areas to establish resource use areas or nature reserves.
- Application of suitable legislation to conserve certain specialized vegetation types (e.g. forests) or mountain areas (e.g. above a certain altitude)

2.4.1 Stewardship Programme

Preliminary discussions with landowners along the Limpopo River, in the Alldays area, close to the Langjan Nature Reserve, south of Louis Trichardt, east and south of Musina and adjacent to the Nwanedi Nature Reserve showed a general willingness amongst landowners to participate in the process. It was decided to try and create blocks of landowners situated in CBA1 areas or areas designated as core areas in the SEMP. Fig. 15 shows the commercial farming areas (brown) that could be targeted to become part of the core area through the stewardship programme. The SEMP proposed zonation (dark green) is shown at the bottom of the figure and the CBA1 (top) and CBA 2 (bottom) zones are also shown for comparison.

Figure 15. Commercial farming areas that could be targeted for conservation expansion through the Stewardship Programme compared with proposed core areas in the SEMP as well as CBA1 and CBA2 in the Ledet C-plan.

2.4.2 The Blouberg- Makgabeng Communal area

We propose the following:

1. That the Blouberg and Maleboch Nature Reserves be connected on the 1200m contour line as shown in Fig. 16 to create one large conservation area. The portion of Blouberg that is added could be legalized as a protected environment, or as one of the other categories listed in the stewardship document. This will probably not impact much on the present legal resource use in the mountain but at least there will be a management plan, rules and law enforcement to prevent further degradation of this unique environment.

Figure 16. Area on the 1200m contour line to be added to the Blouberg area to connect the Blouberg and Maleboch Nature Reserves. Disturbed areas are shown in red

2. That the area of Makgabeng shown in Fig. 17 be designated as one of the stewardship conservation categories. Also, that the feasibility of applying for World Heritage Status for the Makabeng and mission relic sites in the vicinity be investigated. Applications have to be submitted in September so we have a year to compile an application.

Figure 17. The area of Makgabeng to be designated as one of the Stewardship conservation categories

2.4.3 The eastern Soutpansberg

Fig. 18 shows the eastern Soutpansberg region. Green= Nwanedi NR, Mpaphuli NR and western border of the KNP. Red areas are fragmented, blue are the existing Forestry conservation areas (legal conservation areas), light brown shows the area above 1000m altitude, dark brown the area above 1200m and the black line shows the 800m contour line (thanks to Jabu for providing the contour shape files).

Figure 18. The Eastern Soutpansberg Area.

Fig. 18 shows that there is limited space left for conservation expansion due to fragmentation. We propose the creation of the following six legal conservation areas:

Nwanedi NR

We propose that the reserve be expanded to the east along the 800m contour line (light green in Fig. 19) to capture biodiversity in the higher part of the Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld shown in brown. Any of the available legal routes can be followed to achieve this after public participation.

Figure 22. Proposed extension of the Nwanedi NR(light green)
The area south of the Nwanedi NR up to Kruger

We propose that as much as possible of the higher, relatively undisturbed mountain areas be designated under one of the legal categories outlined in the Stewardship Programme. A proposed area is shown in dark green in Fig. 20 with nature reserves in light green and disturbed areas in red.

Figure 20. Proposed conservation extension in the area south of the Nwanedi NR

Vhaghenda Miombo area

Although this vegetation type is relatively small (shown in orange in Fig. 21), it is of high biodiversity importance. We propose an expansion of the Brackenridgea Nature Reserve after public participation along the 800m contour line as shown in the Fig. 2 to approximately 3000 hectares

Figure 21. Location of the Vhaghenda Miombo and proposed extension along the 800m contour line.

See the following paper on the need to expand this nature reserve:

Tshisikhawe, M.P. 2013. Is the resent Brackenridgea Nature Reserve large enough to ensure the survival of *Brackenridgea zanguabarica* Oliv ? Koedoe.

Mphapuli NR

This area is also extremely important from a biodiversity viewpoint and we propose that an attempt be made to expand the size along the 800m contour line as shown in the Fig. 22.

Figure 22. The Mphapuli NR (dull green) and proposed expansion along the 800m contour line.

Thathe Vondo Area

We propose that the three existing Forestry Conservation Areas (Thathe Vondo 1, 2 and 3) be consolidated and expanded along the 1000m contour line as shown in the Fig. 23

Figure 23. Forestry conservation reserves in the Thathe Vondo Area (dark green) and proposed extension along the 1000m contour line (light green).

Matiwa to Ratombo Area

Fig. 24 shows several forestry conservation reserves (blue) in a string extending from Matiwa to Mafela, Entabeni and Ratombo. The surrounding areas seem to be relatively pristine and this allows consolidation and expansion as shown in green. We also propose that it be extended to the south to include part of Tzaneen Sour Bushveld where the Stewardship Programme can be implemented in the commercial farming area. The proposed extension will also include three extremely important lower lying mistbelt forests (light blue).

Figure 24. Forestry conservation reserves between Matiwa and Ratombo and proposed extension.

2.5 Consolidation of the proposed expansion areas into a single core conservation area

The proposed expansion areas discussed in the previous sections are consolidated and combined with the existing core areas to form a single new

proposed core conservation area for the VBR (Fig. 25). The Madimbo Corridor is still being discussed but we have added it in the meantime. The proposed core area provides sufficient connectivity for long term sustainable conservation.

Figure 25. Proposed new core conservation area for the VBR. Existing core areas as well as newly legislated provincial nature reserves and the Madimbo Corridor are shown in bright green. Proposed expansions are shown in dull green and disturbed areas in red.

2.6. A proposed new transitional zone

We propose that the new transition zone be made up by areas that are presently disturbed (red in Fig. 25) and or of economic importance (Fig. 26).

Figure 26. Proposed new transition zones for the VBR shown in orange with the proposed core area in green.

2.7 Buffers

The concept of buffer zones to protect conservation areas has been part of conservation planning since the 1930's and became prominent with the introduction of the Man and Biosphere (MAB) Programme by UNESCO in 1971. The MAB Programme prescribes an integrated conservation and development model requiring that biosphere reserves be divided into core conservation areas, buffer zones and transitional zones. The prime purpose of buffer zones is to protect core conservation areas from impacts by humans but could also serve to reduce the impacts on human populations from crop raiding and predation. It should be pointed out that MAB visualizes core conservation areas as pristine areas with limited human activities while activities such as research, tourism and education take place in surrounding buffer zones. This is in contrast to the situation in most biosphere reserves in South Africa where core areas are utilized for income generating tourism, educational and academic activities and this will also impact on our perception of buffer zones.

Revision of zonation in the VBR requires a clear conceptualization of buffer zones. What should the objectives be, how should they be managed (have we got the resources to manage them effectively), what size should they be, which criteria should be used to determine this, etc., etc.? Ebregt and Greve (2000) present an extensive evaluation of the nature and role of buffer zones that could be used as a basis for planning. They propose a paradigm in which buffer zones not only serve a conservation function but can also address a range of development issues of people in it. They see buffer zone management as a long-term intervention aimed at bringing about a transition to ecological, social, institutional and financial sustainability. In this sense buffer zones should be intensely managed areas that require extensive resources. They also point out that, with development of the ecosystem approach in integrated conservation management, the specific aims of buffer zones should be clearly outlined including the role as a corridor or migration route. In this sense, aspects such as the required size of the buffer, presence of crop raiding animals or predators in the reserve, socio-economic profile of human populations, etc. will impact on the size and management of the buffer zone.

We propose that the concept of buffers be discussed in the workshop on this conservation plan. In the meantime the clear areas surrounding the transition zones shown in Fig. 29 could be seen as buffer zones. The larger open areas north of the mountain can also be described as ecological support areas rather than buffers.

2.8 Species conservation

2.8.1 Plants (information provided by Norbert Hahn)

Plants present a problem because of high diversity and lack of distribution data but we can at least present information on Red Data and Endemic species. The Blouberg and Soutpansberg Mountains are nationally recognized as centers of plant diversity and endemism and should therefore receive the highest possible

conservation status particularly in the higher areas. The mistbelt forest on Blouberg is also listed nationally as a threatened ecosystem.

Fig. 27, based on Table 1, illustrates that the Blouberg, Makgabeng, Soutpansberg and Limpopo River valley are hotspots for the conservation of red data plant species (red dot for each species). It also shows that the new core area will adequately conserve red data plant species. The dots do not indicate specific localities but only the areas in which they occur.

Figure 27. Areas in which red data species of plants occur in the VBR (one dot for each species)

The same general pattern applies to species that are endemic to the VBR (Fig. 31)

Figure 28. Areas in which plant species that are endemic to the VBR occur (one dot for each species)

Fig.29 ,shows the number of endemics per grid in the Soutpansberg. The brown layer is the area above 1000m and it seems that more endemics occur at higher altitudes.

Figure 29. The number of endemic plant species per grid in the Soutpansberg. The area higher than 1000m is coloured brown.

TABLE 1. RED DATA AND ENDEMIC PLANT SPECIES IN THE VBR

VBR_RD_Plant								
Taxon	Con_C	VBR_ED	status	Criteria	Lim	Sout	Blou	Mag
<i>Aloe angelica</i> Pole Evans	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
<i>Aloe hahnii</i> Gideon F.Sm. & R.R.Klopper	No	Yes	NT	B1ab(iii)+2ab(iii)	No	Yes	Yes	No
<i>Aloe petrophila</i> Pillans	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No
<i>Aloe soutpansbergensis</i> Verdoorn	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No
<i>Aloe vogtsii</i> Reynolds	No	Yes	NT	B1ab(iii)+2ab(iii)	No	Yes	No	No
<i>Aloe vossii</i> Reynolds	No	Yes	DDT		No	Yes	No	No
<i>Anisotes rogersii</i> S. Moore	No	Yes			Yes	Yes	No	No
<i>Barleria</i> sp nov	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
<i>Berkheya radyeri</i> Roessler	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	Yes	No
<i>Blepharis spinipes</i> Vollesen	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
<i>Bowiea volubilis</i> Harv. ex Hook.f. subsp. <i>volubilis</i>	Yes	No	VU		No	Yes	No	No
<i>Brackenridgea</i>	Yes	No	CR	A2ad; B1ab(ii,v)	No	Yes	No	No

VBR_RD_Plant								
Taxon	Con_C	VBR_ED	status	Criteria	Lim	Sout	Blou	Mag
zanguebarica Oliv.								
Ceratotheca saxicola E.A.Bruce	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No
Ceropegia cimiciodora Oberm.	Yes	No	VU	B2ab(ii,iii,v)	No	Yes	No	No
Cineraria cyanomontana Cron	Yes	Yes	EN	D	No	No	Yes	No
Cineraria erodioides DC. var. tomentosa Cron	No	Yes	Critically Rare		No	Yes	No	No
Cleome oxyphylla Burch. subsp. robusta Kers	No	Yes			Yes	No	No	No
Clivia caulescens R.A.Dyer	Yes	No	NT	A3d	No	Yes	No	No
Combretum vendae Van Wyk var. glabrata Hahn	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
Combretum vendae Van Wyk var. vendae	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
Conostomium zoutpansbergensis (Brem.) Brem.	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
Cotyledon barbeyi Schweinf. ex Baker var. soutpansbergensis Van Jaarsv. & A.E.van Wyk	No	Yes	Critically Rare		No	Yes	No	No
Curtisia dentata (Burm.f.) C.A.Sm.	Yes	No	NT	A2d	No	Yes	Yes	No
Delosperma zoutpansbergensis L. Bol.	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
Dicliptera cliffordii (K.Balkwill) J.C.Manning & Goldblatt	No	Yes	Rare		Yes	No	No	No
Dicliptera gillilandiorum (K.Balkwill) J.C.Manning & Goldblatt	No	Yes	Rare		Yes	No	No	No
Dicoma montana Schweick.	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Diplolophium buchananii (Benth. ex Oliv.) C.Norman subsp. swynnertonii (Baker f.) Cannon	Yes	No	VU	D2	No	Yes	No	No
Disa extingtoria Rchb.f.	Yes	No	NT	B1ab(iii,iv,v)	No	Yes	No	No
Drimia sanguinea (Schinz)	Yes	No	NT	NT A2d	No	Yes	No	No

VBR_RD_Plant								
Taxon	Con_C	VBR_ED	status	Criteria	Lim	Sout	Blou	Mag
Jessop								
Elaeodendron transvaalense (Burt Davy) R.H.Archer	Yes	No	NT	A4ad	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Encephalartos hirsutus P.J.H.Hurter	Yes	Yes	CR	A4acd; B2ab(iii,iv,v); C1	No	Yes	No	No
Euphorbia aeruginosa Schweick.	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
Euphorbia rowlandii R.A.Dyer	Yes	No	NT	D2	Yes	Yes	No	No
Euphorbia sp. nov.	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
Euphorbia zoutpansbergensis R.A.Dyer	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
Gymnosporia oxycarpa (N.Robson) Jordaan	No	No	Rare		No	No	No	No
Gymnosporia pubescens (N. Robson) M. Jordaan	No	Yes			Yes	Yes	No	No
Huernia nouhuysii Verdoorn	Yes	Yes	VU	D2	No	Yes	No	No
Huernia whitesloaneana Nel	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
Ipomoea bisavium A. Meeuse	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No
Justicia montis-salinarum A.Meeuse	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	Yes	No
Kalanchoe crundallii I.Verd.	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No
Khadia borealis L.Bolus	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	Yes	No
Ledebouria ceruleomontis A.J. Hankey & N. Hahn	No	Yes	VU	D2	No	No	Yes	No
Mystacidium brayboniae Summerh.	No	Yes	NT	D2	No	Yes	No	No
Ocotea kenyensis (Chiov.) Robyns & R.Wilczek	Yes	No	VU	D1	No	Yes	No	No
Orbea conjuncta (A.C.White & B.Sloane) Bruyns	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
Orbea elegans Plowes	Yes	No	CR PE		No	No	Yes	No
Panicum dewinteri	Yes	Yes	NT	B1ab(iii)	No	Yes	Yes	No

VBR_RD_Plant								
Taxon	Con_C	VBR_ED	status	Criteria	Lim	Sout	Blou	Mag
J.G.Anderson								
Pavetta tshikondeni N.Hahn	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No
Pavonia dentata Burt Davy	No	Yes			Yes	No	No	No
Plinthus rehmannii G.Schellenb. (possibly sp nov)	No	Yes			Yes	No	No	No
Prunus africana (Hook.f.) Kalkman	Yes	No	VU A4acd; C1+2a(i)		No	Yes	No	No
Rabdosiella leemannii N.Hahn	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	Yes	No
Rhynchosia vendae C.H.Stirt.	Yes	Yes	VU	B1ab(i,ii,iii,iv,v)	No	Yes	No	No
Sartidia jucunda (Schweick.) De Winter	Yes	Yes	VU	D2	No	Yes	Yes	No
Searsia magalismontana (Sond.) Moffett subsp. coddii (R.Fern. & A.Fern.) Moffett	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Senecio hederiformis Cron	No	Yes	Rare		No	No	Yes	No
Senegalia montis- salinarum N. Hahn	Yes	Yes	ED	B2a D2	No	Yes	No	No
Siphonochilus aethiopicus (Schweinf.) B.L.Burt	Yes	No	CR	A4acd	No	Yes	No	No
Stapelia clavicornata Verdoorn	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
Streptocarpus caeruleus Hilliard & B.L.Burt	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No
Streptocarpus longiflorus (Hilliard & B.L.Burt) T.J.Edwards	Yes	Yes	VU	D2	No	No	Yes	No
Streptocarpus makabengensis Hilliard	Yes	Yes	VU	D1	No	No	No	Yes
Streptocarpus parviflorus Hook.f. subsp. soutpansbergensis Weigend & T.J.Edwards	No	Yes			No	Yes	No	No
Tylophora coddii Bullock	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Vangueria	No	Yes	Rare		No	Yes	No	No

VBR_RD_Plant								
Taxon	Con_C	VBR_ED	status	Criteria	Lim	Sout	Blou	Mag
soutpansbergensis N.Hahn								
Warburgia salutaris (G.Bertol.) Chiov.	Yes	No	EN	A2acd	No	Yes	Yes	No
Zoutpansbergia caerulea Hutch	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Crassula bloubergensis R.A. Dyer	No	Yes			No	Yes	Yes	No

2.8.2 Mammals (excluding bats)

The VBR conserves 112 species of mammals other than bats including about 80% of South Africa's carnivores and three of the "big cats" of the world. Twenty-four species are listed as threatened in the latest SA Red Data Book of Mammals (11 Near Threatened, 6 Vulnerable and 7 Endangered).

Red Data Species

Yellow Golden Mole *Calcochloris obtusirostris* (Near Threatened)

Within the VBR this species only occurs in the Nwambyia Pumbe Sandy Bushveld in the Kruger National Park. The whole VBR population is therefore secure.

Four Toed Elephant Shrew *Petrodromus tetradactylus* (Near Threatened)

Occurs in the Pafuri Forest understory and a population has recently been recorded in the Tshipise Quarter Degree Grid (Mammal Map). The KNP population is secure but the Tshipise population must be included in the core conservation area.

Water Rat *Dasymus robertsii* (Vulnerable)

This rare species is restricted to natural wetlands. It is presently conserved in the Pafuri region of the KNP and in the Luvhondo Private Nature Reserve. All natural marshy wetlands in the VBR are potential hotspots for this species.

Vlei Rat *Otomys auratus* (Near Threatened)

To date this species has only been recorded at one locality in the VBR namely in the eastern Soutpansberg. It occurs in grasslands and wetlands on higher mountain slopes. According to a paper published by Peter Taylor this species seems to be replaced by *O. angoniensis* due to a change in habitat caused by climate change.

Schwartz's White-collared Monkey *Cercopithecus albogularis schwarzi* (Endangered)

This rare subspecies of Samango Monkey is restricted to mistbelt and riparian forests within the VBR. This habitat is legally conserved but it is not enforced and the subspecies is under a lot of threat due to persecution and habitat loss. All mistbelt forest should be highlighted as hotspots for inclusion in conservation areas.

Hedgehog *Atelerix frontalis* (Near Threatened)

Little information is available on the distribution of this species in the VBR but it seems to be declining, possibly due to negative impacts on its preferred habitat, namely grassland and savanna with ample cover. More information needs to be gathered at some stage, for example with a questionnaire survey.

Swamp Musk Shrew *Crocidura mariquensis* (Near Threatened)

Within the VBR it has only been recorded on the southern slopes of the Soutpansberg. All wetlands in these areas are potential hotspots that require conservation. It is presently only conserved in the Luvhondo Private Nature reserve.

Maquassie Musk Shrew *Crocidura maquassiensis* (Vulnerable)

Seems to be restricted to grassland on the southern slopes of the Soutpansberg.

Thin Mouse Shrew *Myosorex cf. tenuis* (endangered)

Only known from moist grassland, wetlands and forest edges on the southern slopes of the western Soutpansberg.

Ground Pangolin *Smutsia temminckii* (Vulnerable)

Although this species is widely distributed in the VBR it is rare and presently under a lot of threat due to electrocution by game fences and the illegal animal trade. It is protected in the KNP, Mapungubwe, Maremane PNR and Luvhondo PNR. Legislation that prescribes electrified game fences to be pangolin friendly will help to conserve this species.

Cheetah *Acinonyx jubatus* (Vulnerable)

Occurs as meta-populations in suitable habitat. Large, unfenced conservation areas with connectivity to conservation areas in neighboring countries will have to be created to ensure the long term survival of this species and others that occur as meta-populations.

Spotted Hyaena *Crocuta crocuta* (Near Threatened)

This species occurs widespread in the savanna areas north of the Soutpansberg and Blouberg and occasionally further south. The Hyaena Distribution Mapping Project is studying the two hyaena species in more detail. It is conserved in large conservation areas along the Limpopo River and into trans-frontier conservation areas.

Brown Hyaena *Hyaena brunnea* (Near Threatened)

Occurs throughout the VBR but is under pressure due to its perceived conflict with livestock farming.

Serval *Leptailurus serval* (Near Threatened)

Associated with wetlands and grassland with long, rank grass throughout the VBR. The conservation of wetlands and associated suitable habitat is important for this species.

Wild Dog *Lycaon pictus* (Endangered)

This species is just holding on in large conservation areas and requires large conservation landscapes for survival.

Leopard *Panthera pardus* (Vulnerable)

Although widespread in the VBR there is concern about a decline in numbers outside conservation areas.

Black Rhinoceros *Diceros bicornis* (Endangered)

This species became extinct in the VBR in the fifties but has been re-introduced into the KNP and private game farms. Its survival is dependent on curtailing poaching for the illegal trade in rhino horn.

Southern White Rhinoceros *Ceratotherium simum simum* (Near Threatened)

Also became extinct in the VBR and later re-introduced. As with Black Rhinoceros all populations are threatened by poaching.

Natal Red Duiker *Cephalophus natalensis* (Near Threatened)

An isolated population of this species occurs in forests and forest margins in the Soutpansberg. Habitat loss, particularly in the east is of concern.

Tsessebe *Damaliscus lunatus* (Vulnerable)

Decline of this species is attributed to a loss of floodplains and other grasslands. It has been re-introduced on game farms.

Roan antelope *Hippotragus equinus* (Endangered)

Historically widespread but its range has been considerably reduced by bush encroachment. Prefers relatively open habitat with a high grass cover.

Sable antelope *Hippotragus niger niger* (Vulnerable)

Historically widely distributed in open savanna woodland with surface water. Has been extensively re-introduced on game farms where gene pools are unfortunately genetically manipulated to suite the hunting industry.

Suni *Neotragus moschatus zuluensis* (Endangered)

Previously recorded in in the Nwambyia Area of the KNP and although there are no recent sightings it may still be present.

Mountain Reedbuck *Redunca fulvorufula fulvorufula* (Endangered)

This species has rapidly declined over the past two decades, probably due to a loss of suitable habitat namely mountain grassland with surface water.

Other species that require conservation attention

Short-snouted Elephant Shrew *Elephantulus brachyrynchus*

This species seem to be relatively rare. It prefers dense grass cover and has been recorded south of Mapungubwe, in the Madimbo Area and south of Blouberg and the Western Soutpansberg.

Elephant *Loxodonta africana*

This species is not on the SA red list but it is listed as Vulnerable by the IUCN so we have to give attention to it. It occurs in the far northern part of the VBR and moves freely between South Africa, Botswana, Zimbabwe and Mozambique.

Cape Hare *Lepus capensis*

This species has only been recorded at one locality in the VBR namely south of Louis Trichardt. It prefers grassland and open habitat avoiding bushy or closed habitat.

Grey Climbing Mouse *Dendromys melanotis*

Distribution records in the SA Red Data Book on Mammals shows that it has a wide distribution in SA extending from the Cape Peninsula to the Limpopo River but excluding the Karoo region. According to this publication it is found in a variety of habitats including grassland, wetland and savanna but is absent from over-grazed regions. All the records from the VBR shown in the map of the Red Data Book are pre 2000 and restricted to the Pafuri and Madimbo area. It has recently been collected in grassland associated with wetlands in the Luvhondo Private Nature Reserve. The species is obviously rare in the VBR and requires attention.

Brant's Climbing Mouse *Dendromus mesomelas*

According to the Red Data Book this species occurs in grassland and marsh vegetation especially in tall grasses. Their map does not show any records from the VBR but it has recently been collected from grassland patches and grass associated with wetlands in the Luvhondo PNR.

Chestnut Climbing Mouse *Dendromus mystacalis*

The Red Data Book only shows pre 2000 records, all from the Pafuri and adjacent regions. It prefers tall, rank grassland.

Hairy Footed Gerbil *Gerbilliscus paeba*

An isolated population of this species apparently occurs in the sandy and dune veld just north of the western end of the Soutpansberg in the vicinity of the Langjan NR. This population has apparently been assigned to the subspecies *G.p. coombsii*. More information will be obtained on its taxonomic status and if it is an isolated subspecies it will enhance the conservation status of this area.

Mozambique Thicket Rat *Grammomys cometes*

This species has only been recorded from a small area in riverine forest in the Pafuri Area. Since riverine forest in this area is impacted on by development in the catchment, its status needs to be monitored.

Four-striped Mouse *Rhabdomys dilectus*

This species has only been recorded in the Soutpansberg within the VBR. It is predominantly a grassland species and will be negatively impacted on by bush encroachment.

Greater Cane Rat *Thryonomys swinderianus*

This species only occurs in wetland and tall grass areas. Habitat change can impact negatively on its conservation status.

Reedbuck *Redunca arundinum*

This species has been eliminated from large areas of its natural range due to habitat loss. It prefers wetlands or drainage lines with tall grass and available surface water

Species that occur in meta-populations

The conservation of viable populations of meta-population species presents one of the most difficult challenges to us. Species such as large carnivores and elephant require very large conservation landscapes that allow free movement and genetic connectivity over large areas. Our target is to conserve viable populations and we propose an ambitious goal to create an open area extending from Limpopo-Lepadi in Botswana, through Mashatu and all along the Limpopo River up to the Kruger National Park and beyond into Zimbabwe and Mozambique. This will require commitment from a range of stakeholders including decision makers in government, rural communities, landowners, business sector and international communities. However, if successful it will create a wilderness area with tremendous international appeal for tourism and create large numbers of jobs, not only in the immediate vicinity but also throughout the VBR. Such a development could be the single most important development for upliftment in the VBR.

Declining habitat specialists

In a recent publication Norbert Hahn showed that at least one of our open grassland biotopes have disappeared and that parts of the VBR is generally characterized by bush encroachment related to factors such as grazing pressure and changed fire regimes. Wetlands are also under pressure and nationally we have already lost 30% of our wetlands. Loss of forest habitat is also of concern in the VBR.

Three of the Red Data species are affected by wetland loss, two by forest decline and seven by a reduction of grassland habitat. Seven of the 11 other species of concern are affected by loss of grassland habitat, one by wetland decline and one by potential impacts on forests.

The private nature reserves created through the Stewardship Programme will have to be managed in such a way that forests, wetlands and grasslands are maintained and enhanced.

Hotspots for rare mammals

Fig. 30 shows the hotspots for Red Data (red dots) and other mammal species of concern (blue dots) with a limited distribution. It shows that the proposed core area should include all the species. All forests, wetlands, grasslands and dune areas are also important.

Figure 30. Locations for Red Data (red dots) and other mammal species of concern (blue dots) with a limited distribution in the VBR.

The impact of climate change

This information was provided by Peter Taylor

The entire species-rich small-mammal community in parts of the VBR are at high risk from climate change as evidenced by papers published on vlei rats *Otomys auratus* and forest shrews *Myosorex*. Fig. 31 on the next page shows a map of *M. cf. tenuis* and *O. auratus* records for Limpopo and predicted suitable areas remaining in 2050. If we believe the models (backed up by historical data), the western Soutpansberg will no longer provide suitable habitat for Sourveld small mammals by 2050, making it really important to secure strongholds in the eastern Soutpansberg – like Entabeni, which is the only site still to retain *Otomys auratus* records.

For more information see:

Taylor et al., 2015. Past, present, and future distribution of afro-montane rodents (Muridae: Otomys) reflect climate-change predicted biome changes. *Mammalia* 2015.

Taylor et al. 2016. South African Mouse Shrews (*Myosorex*) feel the heat : using species distribution models (SDM's) and IUCN Red List criteria to flag extinction risks due to climate change. *Mammal Research*, Springer.

Figure 31. *Myosorex. cf. tenuis* and *Otomys. auratus* records for Limpopo and predicted suitable areas remaining in 2050.

2.8.3 Bats

This information was provided by Peter Taylor.

The VBR is a biodiversity hotspot for bats and conserves 75% of all the bat species that occur in South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland. (46 species). Eight of the species are listed as Threatened in the latest red data book on mammals. A further 18 species are considered to be of conservation concern.

Fig. 32 shows that the majority of Red Data and other bat species of concern were recorded within the proposed core area. The recording of three species in the transition zone south of Thohoyandou at Vygeboom Village require further analysis. All the known bat roosts except one is also situated in the proposed core area.

Figure 32. Localities where red data (red dots) and other bat species of concern (blue dots) have been recorded in the VBR. Known bat roosts are indicated by pink dots.

2.8.4 Birds

Appendix A shows that the VBR conserves 542 bird species, this is more than 50% of the species that occur in southern Africa. Seventy five % of the species are only found in savanna so this is the most important biotope for species diversity. Also, all 42 species listed in the SA Red Data Book on Birds are either restricted to savanna or occur in this biotope. Interestingly none of the grassland or forest restricted species are listed as threatened.

All the Red Data species listed as Critically Endangered are vultures. All breeding sites of these species should therefore be highlighted as conservation hotspots. Eleven species are listed as Endangered and these include one vulture species, two storks, six raptors, one owl and the ground hornbill. All of these will have to be treated individually in the conservation plan. The same applies to the 8 vulnerable species.

One species, the Egyptian Vulture, is considered to be regionally extinct in the VBR

Fig. 34 shows the Important Birding Areas (IBA's) (red) in the VBR as designated by Birdlife South Africa. According to Birdlife South Africa IBA's are places of international significance for the conservation of birds and other biodiversity. They are recognised world-wide as practical tools for conservation and are distinct areas amenable to practical conservation action.

All four IBA's fall within the proposed core area.

Figure 33. Important Birding Areas in the VBR.

Two important vulture breeding colonies occur in the VBR, one in Blouberg and one in the western Soutpansberg,

For more information you are referred to: Ryan van Huyssteen and Melissa Petford: Conservation of birds in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve.
Ryanvanhuyssteen@gmail.com.

2.8.4 Reptiles

This information was provided by Ryan van Huyssteen and Melissa Petford (Soutpansberg Centre for Biodiversity and Conservation)

The VBR conserves 152 reptile taxa (species and subspecies). It is one of southern Africa's most important areas for reptile endemism with 19 endemics. Fourteen taxa are listed as threatened in the SA Red Data Book on Reptiles (3 Data Deficient, 6 Near Threatened, 3 Vulnerable and 2 Endangered).

Red Data reptile species

Crocodylus niloticus (Vulnerable)

Strongholds in major rivers of protected areas Also found in large water bodies on private land.

Homopholis mulleri – (Vulnerable)

Habitats, ecology and distribution poorly known.

Lygodactylus soutpansbergensis (Near Threatened)

Widespread and common in a variety of habitats. Especially summit sourveld and Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld.

Lygodactylus incognitus (Data Deficient)

Comm in Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld, Mistbelt Forest and moist thicket

Lygodactylus montiscaeruli (Data Deficient)

Chirindia langi occidentalis (Vulnerable)

Habitat and ecology poorly known. Abundant on low mountain slopes below 1000 m in the western Soutpansberg. Seems to be associated with clay soils.

Chameasaura aenea (Near Threatened)

Historically recorded in the Soutpansberg but habitat preference unknown. Further research needed to determine occurrence and habitat.

Chameasaura macrolepis (Near Threatened)

Historically recorded in Soutpansberg but habitat preference unknown. Further research needed to determine occurrence and habitat.

Platysaurus monotropis (Endangered)

Restricted to inselbergs in the Makgabeng area. Surrounding plains are vulnerable to habitat destruction. Further research required.

Platysaurus inopinus (Endangered)

Occurs east of the Mogolakwena River. Area where animals occur subject to human pressure from overgrazing and firewood collection. Further research required.

Acontias 'kgalagadi' subtaeniatus (Data Deficient)

Found along the northern slopes of the Soutpansberg and in sandy soil north of mountain.

Acontias richardi (Near Threatened)

Highly restricted north of eastern Soutpansberg. Found at Greater Kudu Land Safaris, and Likely to occur at Nwanedi.

Scelotes albiventris (Near Threatened)

Known from the LangJan and Blouberg Nature Reserve, Nwanedi NR and along the northern Slopes of the Soutpansberg.

Vhembelacerta rupicola (Near threatened)

Widely distributed in the western Soutpansberg. Found from Lajuma Peak on the Luvhondo PNR down into the Sand River.

Figure 35 shows that the Blouberg, Makgabeng and the whole Soutpansberg are hotspots for Red Data and other species of concern. Three red data species occur in the transition zone north of Blouberg and also east and west of Makgabeng and

these will have to be surveyed in more detail to determine whether they should be conserved in special reserves.

Figure 34. The occurrence of Red Data (red dots) and other reptile species of concern (blue dots) in the VBR

2.8.5 Amphibians

This information was provided by Ryan van Huyssteen and Melissa Petford (Soutpansberg Centre for Biodiversity and Conservation)

The VBR conserves 38 species of frogs. Only one species, *Breviceps sylvestris taeniatus* is red listed as Vulnerable. It is restricted to forests and bush clumps of the Soutpansberg. A new species or subspecies related to *B. mossambicus* is being described. It occurs in the Soutpansberg Summit Sourveld. The Pafuri region is a hotspot for frog diversity.

2.8.6 Butterflies

Introduction

This analysis is based on information of the Lepidopteran Society of South Africa. The information is skewed toward the mountainous areas, national parks and nature reserves in the northern and eastern regions while some savanna areas north of the Soutpansberg and the western parts, particularly Blouberg and Makgabeng are under-represented.

This report evaluates the suitability of nine areas (roughly similar to those stipulated in the SEMP) shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35. Areas evaluated for butterfly diversity and rare specie occurrence

Species diversity

A total of 401 species and subspecies of butterflies have been recorded in the VBR by the Lepidopteran Society of SA. This makes up half of the known taxa in South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland.

Figure 36 shows that the highest species/subspecies diversity was recorded in areas 1, 5, 6 and 8, each with more than 200 taxa. The data base contained limited information from area 4.

Figure 36 . Number of butterfly taxa recorded in each area

Fig. 37 shows that a relatively large number of taxa (27%) were only recorded in a single area. All species occurred in at least one area. These figures will probably change as more distribution data becomes available.

Figure 37. Number of areas in which individual taxa have been recorded

Most of the taxa that were only recorded from a single area were found in areas 1, 6 and 8 (60%) (Fig.38).

Figure 38. Number of taxa that have only been recorded in a specific area

**Conservation status (based on Mecenero, et al. 2013.
Conservation assessment of butterflies of South Africa, Lesotho
and Swaziland: red list and atlas).**

Forty one of the taxa that occur in the VBR are listed in the SA or IUCN Red Data List. Thirty of these are Least Concerned Endemics to SA, Lesotho and Swaziland one is a Data Deficient Endemic and 10 are threatened.

Table 2 lists the 10 threatened species of which 2 are Rare Non-endemics, 5 are Rare Endemics, one is an Endangered Endemic(IUCN) and 2 are Critically Endangered Non Endemics. Most threatened species occur in the Blouberg and the Soutpansberg.

TABLE 2. OCCURRENCE OF THREATENED BUTTERFLY SPECIES IN DIFFERENT AREAS OF THE VHEMBE BIOSPHERE RESERVE

SPECIES	CONS. STATUS	OCCURRENCE IN AREA								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Anthene minima minima</i>	Rare					x	x			x
<i>Colotis celimene amina</i>	Rare	x	x	x		x				
<i>Charaxes druceanus solitarius</i>	Rare Endemic				x					
<i>Charaxis Xiphares staudei</i>	Rare Endemic				x					
<i>Dira swanepoeli isolata</i>	Rare Endemic				x					
<i>Orachrysops regalis</i>	Rare Endemic						x			
<i>Papilio ophidocephalus entabeni</i>	Rare Endemic	x	x			x	x	x	x	
<i>Telchinia induna salmontana</i>	Endangered					x	x	x		
<i>Acada biseriata</i>	Critically End.								x	x
<i>Charaxes guderiana guderiana</i>	Critically End.								x	
TOTAL		2	2	1	3	4	4	2	3	2

Eight species or subspecies are endemic to the VBR of which 3 are listed as Least Concerned, 4 as Rare and 1 as Endangered (Table 2). All the species that are endemic to the VBR occur in the Blouberg and Soutpansberg.

TABLE 3. OCCURRENCE OF ENDEMIC SPECIES IN DIFFERENT AREAS OF THE VBR

SPECIES	CONS. STATUS	OCCURRENCE IN C.A.								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Charaxes druceanus entabeni</i>	Least Concerned					x	x	x		
<i>Charaxes druceanus solitaris</i>	Rare Endemic				x					
<i>Charaxes xiphares bavenda</i>	Least Concerned					x	x	x	x	
<i>Charaxes xiphares staudei</i>	Rare Endemic				x					
<i>Dira swanepoeli isolata</i>	Rare Endemic				x					
<i>Dira swanepoeli swanepoeli</i>	Least Concerned					x	x	x		
<i>Papilio ophidocephalus entabeni</i>	Rare Endemic	x	x			x	x	x	x	
<i>Telchinia induna salmontana</i>	Endangered					x	x	x		
TOTAL		1	1	0	3	5	5	5	2	0

Figure 39 shows that the red data and Least Concern VBR endemic species are captured by the proposed core area. The Blouberg and Soutpansberg are hotspots once again.

Figure 39. Occurrence of red data (red dots) and endemic species listed as Least Concern (purple dots).

Discussion

The VBR is an important conservation area for butterflies and contains half of South Africa's species or subspecies including a large number of endemics, eight of which are endemic to the VBR, as well as several threatened taxa. The data base is obviously incomplete, particularly for the Makgabeng to Langjan area, but the following general conclusions can be reached:

- The northern part of the Kruger National Park and the Soutpansberg are diversity hotspots.
- The highest diversity of endemic species occurs in the Soutpansberg.
- The Blouberg and Soutpansberg are hotspots for the conservation of threatened species
- A relatively high number of species were only recorded in one of the nine areas but this may be partly due to deficient sampling.
- All species will be included in at least one of the nine areas studied.
- Distribution maps based on the data set clearly show that core conservation areas should be large enough, either as core, buffer or corridor areas, to include all geomorphological, climatic, plant ecosystems and ecotone types in order to ensure that all species are included. For example, a core conservation area in the Soutpansberg Mountain Bushveld of the Western Soutpansberg should also include ecotones leading to Musina-mopane Bushveld and Makhado Sweet Bushveld to ensure that some species are not excluded.
- The range of at least one species, the globally endangered *Telchinia induna salmontana* has decreased drastically over the past few years due to habitat destruction immediately east of Louis Trichardt and it is now only known to occur at one locality namely the Luvhondo Private nature Reserve.

2.8.7 Scorpions

This information was provided by Ryan van Huyssteen and Melissa Petford of the Soutpansberg Centre for Biodiversity and Conservation

The VBR is a hotspot for scorpion diversity but the only published information is that of Foord *et al.* 2014. Scorpions are widespread in the reserve but important areas are the Pafuri Region, Soutpansberg (especially northern Slopes), Limpopo River, Limpopo Valley, Blouberg, Mogalakwena River and Sand River.

Twenty five 25 species have been recorded in the VBR but we still know little about their distribution and ecology and no conservation assessments have been conducted

Individual species are described because so little information is available.

Species List

Afroisometrus minshullae

The rarest scorpion in the region only known only from a handful of specimens. Very small. Seems to be associated with Tshipise Sandstone and recorded at the Goro Game Reserve, near Musina and at Tshipise.

Uroplectes chubbi

Uncommon, found in moist environments and recorded from Pafuri and Punda Maria in the KNP, Sand River and Mogalakwena River near Tolwe.

Uroplectes flavoviridus

Very similar to *Uroplectes olivaceus* but the last tail segments are more tubular. Common throughout the region and associated with rocky areas. Found from Punda Maria to Vivo and throughout Limpopo Valley. It is common in Western Soutpansberg up to 1200 m a.s.l.

Uroplectes olivaceus

Uncommon in region, localised populations recorded in Soutpansberg at Farm Bergplaat by SCBC. Similar to *Uroplectes flavoviridis*, but tail segments differ.

Uroplectes planimanus

Usually has a distinctive dorsal stripe and is very elongated. Occurs on hot dry mountain slopes and recorded along the Northern Slopes of Soutpansberg and throughout the Limpopo and Sand River Valleys.

Uroplectes carinatus

A common species, associated with northern slopes and other hot areas. Distinguished from similar looking species by the presence of

three prominent keels on tergites.

Uroplectes triangulifer

At least two forms are present in the Soutpansberg where they are abundant at high altitudes. Further work is required to determine whether two species occur.

Uroplectes vittatus

A common arboreal scorpion found in low-lying woodland throughout the VBR but a high altitude form is also found in the western Soutpansberg. Further work is needed to determine whether the high the altitude form is a different species.

Pseudolychas ochraceus

A common scorpion found in various habitats, often around human habitation. Also found in damp situations and one of the few species that tolerate high altitudes.

Pseudolychas pegleri

An uncommon scorpion found in the forests and woodlands of the far eastern Soutpansberg. Similar to *Pseudolychas ochraceus* but distinctly speckled.

Lychas burdoi

A tropical species associated with leaf litter in riverine forest at Pafuri,

Hottentota trilineatus

Abundant scorpion in hot, dry rocky places. Distinguished from other Buthids by a 'lyre' structure found behind the eyes.

Parabuthus granulatus

An uncommon large Buthid associated with sand areas on the northern slopes of the Soutpansberg and western part of the Limpopo River Valley. Could be confused with *Parabuthus transvaalicus*, but is usually dark brown in colour, tail lacks hairiness and telson is smaller than last tail segment. Medically important.

Parabuthus kuanyamarum

Rare. Found in sandy areas north of the far western Soutpansberg. Recorded by SCBC at Bergtop Game Reserve. Also known from Goro Game Reserve.

Parabuthus mossambicensis

Common in flat sandy areas throughout the VBR.

Parabuthus transvaalicus

An abundant scorpion associated with sandy, rocky and wooded areas at low altitudes throughout the VBR. Large black scorpion with hairy tail. Medically important with a very painful sting.

***Hadogenes soutpansbergensis* (western Soutpansberg endemic)**

Found in rocky habitats at all altitudes in the western Soutpansberg.

Hadogenes troglodytes

A large scorpion, males can grow up to 21cm in length. Found in low-laying rocky areas.

***Opisththalmus lawrencei* (western Soutpansberg endemic)**

Common in sandy areas of the western Soutpansberg, often under rocks.

Opisththalmus boehmi

Locally common. Found on flat sandy areas in western parts of the VBR

Opisththalmus glabrifons

A large species found at low altitudes throughout the VBR

Opisththalmus wahlbergii

Marginally represented in the far western Soutpansberg (recorded at Bergpan}. Likely to occur from foothills of Soutpansberg to Mogolakwa River.

Cheloctonus jonesii

Common in the VBR. Similar to *Opisthacanthus* it makes distinctive vertical burrows into nearly any substrate.

Opisthacanthus asper

A common tree dwelling species found at low altitudes throughout the VBR.

Opisthacanthus sp. (western Soutpansberg endemic)

An undescribed species from high altitudes in the western Soutpansberg. Lives under rocks on sandy substrate. And seems to favour moist environments. It is common in the Luvhondo Private Nature Reserve.

Further Reading

Foord, S.H., Gelebe, V., and Prendini, L. 2014. The Effects of Aspect and Altitude on Scorpion Diversity along an Environmental Gradient in the Soutpansberg, South Africa. *Journal of Arid*

2.8.8 Spiders

This information was provided by Stefan Foord.

Figure 40 shows that all the listed Red Data and endemic spider species occur in the Blouberg and Soutpansberg mountains.. Numerous spider species still need to be described and some have not even been assigned to genera yet. A brief survey in the western Soutpansberg revealed one of the highest spider diversities ever recorded in Africa.

Figure 40. Areas where Red Data (red dots) and endemic (blue dots) spiders have been recorded in the VBR.

2.9 The conservation of aquatic ecosystems in the VBR

This information was provided by Paul Fouche

Wetlands

TABLE 3. WETLANDS THAT OCCUR IN THE VBR

Wetland class	Examples	Examples in the VBR	Location
1. Endorheic	Flats, pans and marshes	Soutpan, farm Zoutpan Leeupan (Mapungubwe NP)	22° 57' S and 29° 24' E
2. Riverine	Perennial rivers	Luvuvhu River and tributaries, Nzhelele River, Mutale River and tributaries <u>Special aspects associated with the class</u> 1. Limpopo pans, Pafuri. 2. Den Staat, (Mapungubwe NP)	22° 20' - 22° 25' S 31° 00' - 31° 15' E
	Seasonal rivers	Limpopo River, Sand River, Mogalakwena River	
2. Lacustrine	Freshwater lakes	Lake Fundudzi	22° 51' S and 30° 18' E
3. Palustrine	Permanent freshwater marshes and swamps	Zwavhavili, Mphapuli	22° 47' S and 30° 39' E
	Peatlands and fens	Farm Bergplaats Farm Ontmoet Mutale peatland Vhembe farm den Staat	23° 02' S and 29° 26' E 23° 02' S and 29° 23' E 22° 52' S and 30° 20' E 22° 12' S and 29° 15' E
	Springs and oases	Farm Scot Madimuhulu, farm Septimus Farm Potgietersrust Sand River Farm Robertson <u>Hotsprings</u> Evangelina Farm Sulphur Springs Tshipise Aventura Mphephu Aventura Resort	22° 57' S and 29° 24' E 22° 14' S and 30° 13' E 22° 00' S and 29° 28' E 22° 56' S and 29° 37' E 22° 25' S and 29° 12' E 22° 49' S and 29° 52' E

Fish diversity in the VBR

The VBR is drained by the Limpopo River system. This is the most diverse system in South Africa with eleven fish families and 50 species. Forty four species are conserved in the VBR.

All the perennial rivers could be regarded as the hotspots that require conservation.

Seven species are endemic to the system and the adjacent Incomati and Phongolo systems, a further two are endemic to this system and the systems further south and nine species are endemic to the Kunene/Okovango/Zambezi systems. Four species are endemic to the system and one of these, *Notobranchius orthonotus* are found in the VBR. Three of the species found in the VBR are listed in the SA Red Data Book on Freshwater Fishes namely *Notobranchius orthonotus* and *Opsaridium peringueyi*, listed as rare, and *Notobranchius furzeri* which is listed as endangered.

Aquatic conservation hotspots in the VBR

The following aquatic systems are considered to be important

- The Mukhase River in the Mphaphuli Cycad Reserve. Unique due to the occurrence of rare fish species including the Red Data species *Opsaridium peringueyi*.
- Lake Fundudzi. Unique as the only freshwater inland lake in South Africa and because of its heritage
- The Nwanedi River as it provides the only location of the rare catfish species, *Clarias theodora*.
- The Salt pans north of the Soutpansberg due to their vegetation and associated species.
- The Floodplains in the lower reaches of the Limpopo and Luvuvhu Rivers.
- All wetlands with peat deposits.
- Perennial streams in upper reaches of the Soutpansberg and Blouberg because of their unique invertebrate and vertebrate species. For example, the mountain streams in the Western Soutpansberg provide suitable breeding sites for the extremely rare Black Cruiser Dragonfly. One of these sites is now threatened by illegal forest clearing and water extraction on a neighboring property.
- All endorheic wetlands are important because they provide essential specialized habitats for frogs, birds and a variety of other vertebrates and invertebrates. Grassland associated with wetlands are also important for a variety of antelope species.
- All rivers and associated riverine forests are important because they provide migration routes for mammals and birds. They are also used as corridors by species such as leopard.
